

**Microcredentials and Skill Enhancement Aligning With
NEP 2020: Transforming Role of Academic Libraries**

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Abstract:

Academic libraries play a vital role in the implementation of the “National Education Policy NEP/ 2020”. Microcredentials and other skill enhancement opportunities by integrating ICT tools, digital content management, and supporting learning pathways for micro credential courses that are skill-driven, and stackable under frameworks like the “National Credit Framework (NCrF)” and “Academic Bank of Credits (ABC)”.

This transformation reflects a strategic shift in library services from passive repositories to dynamic learning facilitators. It also strengthens research, critical thinking, life skills, digital empowerment, and holistic development. The academic libraries empower students to acquire vocational skills. It helps to build interdisciplinary knowledge for employability and global recognition. Identifying the contribution of “microcredentials” for career and professional upliftment is an essential outcome of this paper. The paper also suggests the scope of academic libraries in furthering the scope of microcredentials.

1.Introduction

A “microcredential” is a certification designed to gain specific skills or competencies. These concise credentials are competency-based and assessed according to clear standards, and awarded by universities, colleges, industry bodies, or reputable online platforms. They may stand alone or can be “stackable” for higher grades like diplomas or degrees.

Microcredentials emphasise the specific skills or learning outcomes. It is most suited for workforce needs that are relevant to industry. The “microcredentials” are flexible and short courses offered in online, offline, and blended modes. Competency is verified through assessments and the learner earns a credential after completion of the course. Microcredentials are portable. Upskilling at one’s own pace, saving the time and cost to attain a full degree for gaining competency in relevant interdisciplinary areas and addressing skill gaps as per the demand of the evolving sectors of employment, stackable to a full degree makes microcredentials popular.

The traditional learning framework integrates 21st-century skills into higher education. A pivotal aspect of this policy is the emphasis on “flexible learning pathways, “interdisciplinary education”, and “lifelong learning”, with a strong focus on “skill development”. Micro-credentials are pivotal

in actualizing the “National Education Policy (NEP) 2020’s” vision for higher education in India as an innovative tool for learners to acquire targeted, market-relevant skills outside conventional degree programs .

These skill-focused certifications enable students to gain effective knowledge in emerging fields of knowledge and expertise that cater to the learners. Microcredentials can facilitate seamless academic progression.

2.Literature Review

According to Oliver (2019), microcredentials are “a certification of assessed learning that is additional, alternate, or complementary to traditional qualifications”. Microcredentials provide learners with specific skills and competencies that meet the demands of employers. As per the requirements for employability and the industry trends, microcredentials are helpful. Microcredentials account for competency-based education.

UNESCO (2021), highlights the global significance of microcredentials in promoting “inclusive and equitable” quality education. They empower learners to upskill rapidly, often through online platforms, offering flexibility, accessibility, and cost-effectiveness.

NEP 2020 and Skill Enhancement initiatives integrate vocational education with credit-based modular learning. It enables the learners to accumulate and transfer credits from diverse learning experiences, including microcredentials (MHRD, 2020).

According to Raju (2017), libraries are evolving to support user-centric, skill-oriented education.

As per the reports of the esteemed news dailies, “Indian Express”, “Times of India”, “Hindustan times” and “economic times,” 21% of learners who completed professional certificates found new jobs, and 32% got a salary boost”, “A striking 96% of Indian students believe professional micro credentials enhance employability”, hiring managers are 85% more likely to choose candidates with certified, job-focused microskills”. Around 26% of higher-ed leaders cite inconsistent quality as a barrier and coordinating among regulatory bodies is a rather complex process. EdTech and NSQF platform partnerships are taking place under government initiatives.

According to Coursera’s 2024 report, 21% of learners who are Indians, with professional certificates had got jobs, and 32% had gains in their remuneration. A study from a tier-2 institution in India found that students frequently mentioned “empowerment” (quality and global access), “recognition” (profile-building), and the value of “institutional support” in completing MOOCs.

3.Discussion

3.1. Microcredentials landscape in India

According to the “Coursera Micro Credentials Impact Report 2024 India Edition”, micro credentials enhance graduates’ job readiness. 52% of Indian institutions offer credit-bearing

microcredentials, with 94% planning to integrate them into degree programs.”NEP/ 2020" encourages integrating vocational, digital, and skill-based learning into traditional degrees.”National Credit Framework (NCrF)” allows up to 50–70% of degree credits from courses that enhance the skill.Academic Bank of Credits (ABC) accumulates, stores, and transfers credits.

“Vishwakarma Institute of Information Technology(Pune)”,and many universities partner with Coursera, Udemy, SWAYAM, and NPTEL to offer industry-aligned microcredentials.

Programs with Google, Microsoft, and IBM are often aligned with frameworks like “NSQF”.

India is rapidly embracing microcredentials. Propelled by vision, institutional adoption, robust educational technology partnerships, credit systems, and positive student outcomes, these credentials are already proving their power in enhancing employability. SWAYAM offers thousands of courses. Crores of enrollment show a higher accessibility of the courses.

“SWAYAM”, “NPTEL”, “Coursera”, “edX”, and many other platforms curate microcourses. SWAYAM & NPTEL have a high scale of student engagement.NPTEL certifications from IIT/ IISc are trusted by participating colleges. NPTEL/SWAYAM are increasingly incorporating AI-driven personalization, local language options, and interactive learning tools for wider outreach.

SWAYAM/ Plus augments SWAYAM by delivering industry-linked courses e.g. Microsoft, Cisco.

ABC credit portability across institutions enables learners to accumulate micro-credential credits.

UGC’s 2024 guidelines empower HEIs to develop and offer SWAYAM credit courses within their existing programs, allowing degree credits to come from micro-credentials.

In West Bengal, credit-bearing micro-credentials are steadily gaining importance across universities and colleges.

Maulana Abul Kalam Azad University of Technology, West Bengal or MAKAUT, has integrated MOOCs into its B.Tech curriculum.MOOCs are treated as “equivalent to theoretical courses”. Under UGC’s Credit Framework for Online Learning, AICTE’s mandate states that “up to 20%” of credits per semester may come from SWAYAM-based coursework/.

NPTEL local chapter in Kolkata”, facilitates course delivery and charting processes for credit transfers. Many affiliated colleges appoint SPOCs (Single Point of Contact) to streamline MOOC registrations, campus exam administration, and transcript uploads.

West Bengal’s higher education institutions are successfully embedding credit-bearing micro-credentials through MOOCs.

Institutions are encouraging microlearning. A few of the initiatives are IIT, through which “NPTEL” offers micro courses in subjects like machine learning, blockchain, and renewable energy. These courses are recognized under the credit transfer.

IGNOU promotes open and distance learning through certifications and microcredentials.

3.2. Learning pathways under NEP/ 2020

Certifications relevant for commerce graduates include, “digital marketing certificate”, which covers skills such as content marketing, and digital advertising. Microsoft “Power/ BI” certification enables proficiency in data visualization and business intelligence using Power BI. Certified Digital Marketing Professional (CDMP) validates knowledge and skills in digital marketing, making it a valuable asset for career advancement. “Certified Financial Planner (CFP)” is highly relevant for careers in finance and investment. Google Ads Skillshop trains for online advertising. “Excel”, “SQL” and other programming languages are essential for data analysis skills. E-commerce certifications help gain skills in online retail, brand development, and e-commerce. “Financial Accounting & Analysis Microcredential”, “Business Analytics Foundations” on data analysis techniques and their application in business contexts for commerce graduates.

The certifications that are relevant for the students of science streams include, “Python programming language”, “data analytics”, “elements of data science”, “Databases”, “Cybersecurity Fundamentals” etc.

The certifications relevant for students of the arts stream include “Professional writing”, “theatre in healing & education” etc.

Interdisciplinary micro credentials include “digital marketing”, “data science and analytics”, “AI and Machine Learning”, “cybersecurity”, “investment and stock market”, “graphic design and UI/UX”, communication skills, and soft skills.

These micro credentials (3 6/ months or 30–40/ hours) blend seamlessly with undergraduate studies boosting employability, project portfolios, and readiness for multidisciplinary careers.

A step-by-step overview for learners

Academic Bank of Credits (ABC) Setup. Students register via Digilocker, UMANG, or the ABC portal to obtain a unique ABC ID, linked to their university or institution. HEIs (universities/ colleges) register on the ABC portal, designate nodal officers, and synchronize student data through Samarth or in-house ERP systems. Students can enroll in SWAYAM or NPTEL MOOCs approved by their institution. Universities pre-approve certain MOOC courses for credit transfer and appoint “SPOC” or nodal officers to manage registration, exam scheduling, certificate receipt, and transcript updates. Universities may conduct SWAYAM end-term exams on campus, replacing previous central proctoring arrangements. After completion, earned credits appear in the student’s ABC dashboard. To pursue another program or continue studies, students can transfer credits between HEIs through ABC. Credits once redeemed can’t be reused. The

credit system enables NEP-aligned multiple entry and exit options. To verify a microcredential's status on university sites, a learner must look for phrases like "credit-bearing microcredential," "X credits," "stackable certificate", or reference to recognized frameworks.

Non-university platforms (e.g. Coursera, edX) should clearly state if a course is "for credit" or just "a certificate or a badge".

The learner must inspect the "badge metadata" to confirm outcomes and official credit value.

Credit-bearing & stackable microcredentials are academically rigorous, give official credits, and build toward real credentials.

Non-credit microcredentials or short courses focus on skills and recognition. Academic credit is not obtained. Badges are a record of skills but rely on underlying credential structures.

3.3. Opportunities of academic libraries

Academic libraries can serve as gateways for microcredential platforms and initiatives. Academic libraries can support NEP's multidisciplinary vision. NEP 2020 encourages "interdisciplinary education", and libraries can give access to cross-disciplinary content. Libraries can index institutionally developed microcredentials in library repositories. Libraries can facilitate research and learning in emerging domains such as AI, digital humanities, environmental studies, and other domains. Libraries can encourage blended and hybrid learning models by enhancing digital infrastructure. Libraries can integrate microcredentials into learning management systems (LMS) and digital repositories. Academic libraries can assist in hosting the content. Channeling students for microlearning can be through assistance for enrollment and certification processes. Libraries can assist in recording, storing, and tracking learners' certifications.

Libraries can support faculty in aligning microcredentials with semester-wise curriculum and learning outcomes. Developing information and digital literacy in the age of microlearning is vital. Libraries can conduct workshops on the significance of "microcredentials" and learning pathways to popularise among learners. Seminars and webinars on navigating MOOCs can be regularly organised. The libraries can support learners by curating a list of courses. Technical assistance for MOOCs shall be an essential function of the academic libraries. The libraries can help in evaluating e-learning content, and open-source platforms. Libraries can help to assess the credibility of digital learning content. Librarians can contribute to resource development through content curation. They can collaborate with faculty to develop MOOCs.

The librarians can encourage faculty-librarian collaboration to co-create instructional content. The library supports learners with self-learning materials. Libraries provide learning resources. Academic libraries can assist skill-building among diverse learners across rural and urban India.

Indian micro credential platforms have achieved significant adoption, scale, and impact. Credit-bearing recognition, high engagement, and positive outcomes validate their effectiveness. Yet maintaining consistent quality and regulatory cohesion is crucial as the ecosystem matures. The

need for consistent quality standards and streamlined accreditation procedures can be addressed by identifying the causes. Low completion rates are often visible. Libraries can support learner motivation, engagement, and help in overcoming language barriers.

User interactions on MOOCs, microlearning, problems, and concerns can be an effective contribution of the libraries. In some instances, actual course use and certification are limited due to infrastructure, time constraints, and language. Academic libraries can address the problems to solve the underlying issues in maximising enrollment for microcredentials.

4. Conclusion

The intersection of microcredentials, skill development, and NEP 2020 offers a transformative pathway. Academic libraries are no longer passive participants but active enablers of this transformation. By curating digital content, enabling credit-based learning, fostering digital literacy, and supporting lifelong learning, libraries are becoming pivotal in ensuring that microcredentials are not just accessible but also meaningful in a rapidly evolving knowledge society.

The academic libraries have a scope for innovation. Libraries can reinforce microcredentials through policy support, capacity building, and technological upgrades. Embracing microcredentials is not just a trend but a necessity for academic institutions, and libraries are the catalysts for new educational architecture.

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